

**HYDROGEOPHYSICAL STUDIES TO EXPLORING
GROUNDWATER AQUIFER AROUND EL-FAYOUM
DEPRESSION, EGYPT**

By

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A thesis submitted in partial fulfillment
for the requirements of the degree of
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Department of Geology
Faculty of Science, Fayoum

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Dedication

I would like to thank and dedicate this work

To

My Parents,

To

My Wife,

And To

My brothers

Abstract

Desert area around El Fayoum depression considered as one of the most important places in Egypt for the reclamation process that depends mainly on the groundwater. On the other hand, studies which relates to the exploration and evaluation of groundwater in this area are considered rare. Vertical electrical sounding and hydrogeochemical analysis had been performed for evaluation and understanding the relation between Quaternary and Eocene aquifers in the study area. Eighty-seven vertical electrical soundings (VES) were carried out as well as 60 water samples were collected in the study area. The electrical data was interpreted by using IX1D V3 software where the true resistivity and thickness of each layer was calculated. Based on the inversion results, a set of geoelectrical cross-sections have been constructed. From the interpreted electrical data the Quaternary aquifer is composed from sand to sandy clay deposits and exhibit low thickness and resistivity ranges. The upper most part of the Eocene aquifer was detected and consists of marly limestone with low groundwater potentiality. The collected water samples were chemically analyzed in the water quality central laboratory of Fayoum Drinking Water and Sanitation Company. The chemical analysis of the water samples revealed that the salinity increase toward El-Fayoum Lakes. 37.5 % samples of Quaternary aquifer are suitable for irrigation use while 62.5 % samples of Quaternary aquifer and water samples collected from Eocene are not suitable for irrigation under ordinary condition due to its high salinity, but special management for salinity control may be required and salt tolerant plants should be selected.

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Chapter One

Introduction

El-Fayoum meaning lake or sea according to the Coptic word phiom or pa-youm. The Fayoum depression looks like a delta in its triangular shape. El-Fayoum governorate is a potential place for urban developments and touristic activities. Agriculture is the main activity in El-Fayoum district. Over 340000 feddans are cultivated and 12613 now under reclamation process.

In the study area, the exploration of groundwater is actually very limited. Hydrogeophysical studies will be used to facilitate solving near-surface structure and evaluating of the groundwater resources (Quaternary and Eocene limestone aquifers). The geoelectrical resistivity survey is planned to provide information on depth to water, aquifer thickness and its hydraulic characteristics. These studies help us to obtain a recommended strategy for groundwater development in the future.

1.1. Main objective(s):

The main objective of the thesis is exploring and evaluating groundwater in the reclaimed lands around El-Fayoum depression by using geophysical techniques, hydrogeological and geological studies. Since this desert area represent extension for reclamation projects around El-Fayoum governorate.

1.2. Location of the Study Area:

The study area is bounded by Latitudes $29^{\circ}00'$, $29^{\circ}45'N$ and Longitudes $30^{\circ}15'$, $31^{\circ}15'E$ (Fig.1).

Figure (1): Location map of the study area.

1.3. Previous Work:

Many authors studied the surface geology and geomorphology of the study area and their surroundings. e.g. Blanckenhorn (1901), Lucas (1902) Beadnell (1901; 1905), Hume (1912), Sandford and Arkell (1929), Gardner and Caton-Thompson (1926), Little (1936), Ball (1939), Iskander (1943), Fox (1952), Ibrahim (1951), Shukri and Azer (1952), Shata, Knetsch *et al.* (1962), Said (1962, 1990), Tamer (1968), Shamah (1981), Abdel Kireem (1971), Khalifa, *et al.* (1993), Swedan (1986), Bown and Kraus (1988), and others. Blanckenhorn (1901) suggested that El-Fayoum depression was originated by faulting. Beadnell (1901;1905) published some of the most extensive work ever done on the tectonic history and depositional environments of Eocene through recent strata of El-Fayoum. The rock units of El-Fayoum depression and its vicinities are ranging in age from Tertiary to Quaternary. The only igneous rocks in the area (basalt sheets and flows) exposed at Wadan El-Faras and Gabal Qatrani at the northern part of the investigated area. One of the features characterizes the stratigraphy of the depression is the constancy of many of beds over a wide area. Gardner and Caton-Thompson (1926) assumed the origin of El-Fayoum area is wind erosion, which began during Pliocene, thus, they advocated Beadnell's proposal (1905) and unacceptable Sandford and Arkell's hypotheses (1929) of Post-Pleistocene fluvial erosion as the main agent of excavation. Gardner (1926) memoir depicted the Pleistocene and recent lacustrine environment and gave clues of Palaeolithic and historic man in El-Fayoum depression. Sandford and Arkell (1929) gave in detail a description of Pleistocene-recent Nile Valley and lake terraces of El-Fayoum depression and recapped the paleodepositional setting of it. They construct a regional geologic map of El-Fayoum- Nile divide with cross sections of different units and geomorphic features besides the brief description of Eocene–Pliocene strata. Caton-Thompson and Gardner (1934) underlined in their work on the geomorphology and the stratigraphy of El-Fayoum-Beni Suef area. They gave a detailed description of the stratigraphic sequence in the northern end of El-Fayoum depression and mapped faults and folds and briefly discussed them. Simplified geological map of this region was also published. They compared their work with the previous studies and noticed that little regarding the stratigraphic of El-Fayoum has been published since working

of Beadnell (1905). They considered the Fayoum originated by a complex tectonic activity, water erosion during wet climate, chemical weathering of calcareous rocks and wind abrasion when arid condition prevailed. Little (1936) briefly described the Eocene–Pliocene sedimentary section. He interested the sediments and lake level of Pleistocene-Holocene Lake Qarun in this work. Said (1990) discussed the Eocene succession exposed at El-Fayoum depression based on lithological and paleontological data given by Beadnell (1905) (Table.1). His report included a description of depositional environments of the Eocene to recent sediments.

The hydrogeological conditions of El-Fayoum depression were studied by authors; Lucas (1902), Hume (1912), Arafa (1947), Attia (1951), Fox (1952), Shata, *et al.* (1962), Tamer and Fahim (1987), Himida (1970), Zahran (1973), Abdel-Baki (1972), Diab (1972), Meshal (1973), El-Hakeem (1977), Bishai and Kirollus (1980), Himida (1980), Hady, *et al.* (1982), Ezzat (1982), Shata (1982), Fahiem (1985), Deser Research Institute (1986), Dahab (1988), Hamza, *et al.* (1988), Al-Naggar *et al.* (1989), Shedid (1994), Garbrecht (1996), El-Shabrawy and Dumont (2009), Basheer and Taha (2012) and El-Kammar *et al.* (2015) gave a general review of the parameters and characteristics of the surface and the groundwater aquifers in the study area.

Table (1): Middle and Upper Eocene rock units in Egypt (Said, 1990)

LATE	GROUP	SUB GROUP	Plank. Foram. Zones	NUMMULITE ZONES	GEBEL MOKATTAM	HELWAN	GIZEH PYRAMIDS PLATEAU	GEBEL ATAQA	NILE	FAYUM	NORTH BAHARIYA	GULF OF SUEZ	
				MAADI	MAADI	MAADI	MAADI	MAADI	MAADI	MAADI	MAADI	MAADI	MAADI
M I D D L E	M O K A T T A M	O B S E R V A T O R Y	P 19-18	N(A)	MAADI	Wadi Hof 65m 25m		/ / / / /	/ / / / /	Maadi	Qasr El Sagha 180m 30m		Bir Heleriya
			N(B)	Wadi Garawi 25m 10m		110m	Gehannam				/ / / / /	Tanka	
			N(C)	52m		97m	13m				Beni Suef 86m	50m	/ / / / /
	M O K A T T A M	O B S E R V A T O R Y	P 13-12	N(D)	Giushi 33m	Observatory -136m	Giushi (?) Concealed	El Ramiya 78m	El Fashn 70m	Gharaq 40m	Sath El Hadid 10m	Khaboba	93m
			N(E)	Upper Building Stone 70m	Gebel Hof 121m	Observatory 16m	Suez 224m	Qarara 170m	Midawara 80m	Hamra 43m			
			N(F)	Lower Building Stone 27m	/ / / / /	Mokattam 90m	/ / / / /	Maghagha 80m	Muweilih 30m	Qazzun	Darat		
			N(G)	/ / / / /	/ / / / /	/ / / / /	/ / / / /	Samalut 160m	Minia	Naqab 29m	/ / / / /		
M I N I A	M O K A T T A M	O B S E R V A T O R Y	P 10-11	N(G)	/ / / / /	/ / / / /	/ / / / /	/ / / / /	115m	29m	/ / / / /	98m	

Chapter Two

Geological Setting

El-Fayoum province is one of the deep depressions in the Western Desert of Egypt situated immediately west the Nile Valley, about 70 km southwest of Cairo. Its total area is about 6068 km². The depression is connected with the River Nile through Bahr Yousif at Hawara, which it is considered the only source of water. Blanckenhorn (1901) stated that the origin of El-Fayoum depression was a tectonic movement where faults bounded the depression on all sides. The oldest rock unit of the depression began in the Jurassic Period along the Tethyan margin and its current shape resulted from tectonic subsidence that finalizes in the Late Eocene Epoch (Massoud *et al.* 2009). El-Fayoum area lies within stable shelf that covered by the Eocene shale, limestone, and sandstone (Said, 1990). Its slopes generally northward and surrounded by scarps and plateaux in most parts, so it is similar to the other depression in the Western Desert but it differs in the existence of Nile silt which covers the floor of the depression. El-Fayoum depression is primarily divisible into four distinct parts- cultivated land, Qarun Lake, Wadi El-Rayan and the surrounding desert region. High topographic areas, like Gabal El-Naalun, Gabal El-Lahun on the eastern and southern sides and Gabal Qatrani in the north are bounded El-Fayoum depression.

2.1. Geomorphology:

Many authors studied geomorphology of E-Fayoum basin and its vicinities, like Tamer (1968), Abdel-Baki (1972), Brewer (1989), Said (1990), Shedid (1994), Usama (2000), Ibrahim .M (2000) and others. The area under investigation and its vicinities can be divided into the following geomorphic units:

1.1. The depressions.

1.2. Lakes.

1.3. Aeolian Landforms:

1.4. The alluvial plains.

1.5. Escarpments.

2.1.1. The depressions:

The study area has two main morphotectonic depressions; El-Fayoum and Wadi El-Rayan depressions. The first is a circular depression which covers an area about 1700 km². It is closed with an altitude ranging from +24 m above sea level at Lahun area to -45 m below sea level at Qarun Lake. The eastern and northern portion of the depression covered by the Eocene and Oligocene sediments that are characterized by the absence of any drainage lines and agricultural activity (Abdel-Baki, 1972). Wadi El-Rayan depression is isolated and uninhabited depression situated southwest El-Fayoum, at -60 m below sea level (b.s.l) representing the famous low landforms on the northeastern side of the Western Desert. This part of El-Fayoum attracted the attention of the scientists especially geologists because of its possible future as a reservoir. It is covered an area of about 706 km² (170,000 feddans). The depression is separated from El-Fayoum by limestone ridge (Gisr El-Hadid plateau) and is bounded on all sides by highlands e.g., Gabal El-Mishigiega (+96 m a.s.l). The ground surface of Wadi El-Rayan depression is covered by sabkha, sand dunes, and sand plains.

2.1.2. Lakes:

El-Fayoum depression contains natural and artificial lakes. The Wadi El-Rayan lakes (upper and lower lake) represented the artificial lakes which were formed in 1973 as a result of excess agricultural drainage water from El-Fayoum region, with an area of 50.9 km² and 62 km² respectively. The two lakes have different altitudes; therefore, a waterfall was created where they meet. The natural lake is represented by Lake Qarun (Its ancient name Lake Mories) which is situated to the north of El-Fayoum. It is covering an area of about 235 km².

2.1.3. Aeolian Landforms:

Aeolian landforms are found in regions of the earth where erosion and deposition by the wind are the dominant geomorphic forces shaping the face of the landscape. Regions influenced by the wind include most of the dry climates of the

earth; this would include regions of the world that are classified as arid deserts and semiarid steppe. The wind can also cause erosion and deposition in environments where sediments have been recently deposited or disturbed. The relative ability of wind to erode materials is slight when compared to the other major erosional mediums, water, and ice, because of their greater density. The Aeolian landforms are represented mainly by the following features:

A. The sand dunes:

Sand dunes are the most noticeable landforms produced by wind erosion. The largest dune fields are found in the Middle East and North Africa. A "dune field" is an area covered by extensive sand dunes. In the study area, the depositional landforms are spread especially in Wadi El-Rayan depression and north of Lake Qarun.

B. Desert pavement:

Desert pavements are smooth, old, stone surfaces that commonly occur on abandoned alluvial units in arid terrain (Engel and Sharp, 1958). They are a layer of pebbles left behind after the wind remove fine particles from the surface (deflation process). In the study area, the desert pavement is well developed along the eastern flat side.

C. Yardangs Mushroom Rocks and Ventifacts:

Wind action produced several distinctive desert features, such as mushroom rocks, ventifacts, and yardangs. Mushroom rocks are formed when the wind blows sand around the bottom of the rock wearing it away. Ventifacts are rocks that have been abraded, pitted, etched, grooved, or polished by wind-driven sand. Yardangs are a large area of soft, poorly consolidated rock and bedrock surfaces that have been extensively grooved, fluted, and pitted by wind erosion. The rock is eroded into alternating ridges and furrows essentially parallel to the dominant wind direction. The above mentioned forms occur on the western side of El-Fayoum depression, especially in Wadi El-Hitan area.

2.1.4. The alluvial plains:

The area under investigation and its vicinities have two types of alluvial plains (old and young alluvial plains) according to its age. The young alluvial plain occupies

the old cultivated lands with an area 2500 km² with the exception of Lake Qarun and part of Wadi El-Rayan depression, covering the lowest part of El-Fayoum depression. Its origin and composition are identical with the river alluvium of Nile Valley. These plains dissected by the irrigation canals and agriculture drains of less extent. The old alluvial plains exposed as terrace forms found around El-Fayoum depression and absent in Wadi El-Rayan depression. These plains are lacking any drainage lines and vegetation.

2.1.5. Escarpments:

El-Fayoum depression is surrounded by scarps and structural calcareous plateau in most parts, like Gabal El-Naalun in the east, which is composed of limestone, marl and sandstone of Eocene age and covered by gravels and sand of Pliocene Period, Gabal El-Lahun in the south, Gabal Qatrani and sandstone of Oligocene age in the north, Gisir El-Hadid plateau in the southwest and Garet-Gehannam plateau in the west (limestone plateau) of El-Fayoum depression.

2.2. Stratigraphic Successions:

The rock units in El-Fayoum depression and its vicinities are of sedimentary origin (Fig.2), ranging in age from Tertiary to Quaternary. The only igneous rocks in the area are represented by basalt sheets in the north of Gabal Qatrani. The stratigraphic succession of the study area has been discussed by many authors e.g. Blanckenhorn (1901), Beadnell (1905), Hume (1912), Cuvillier (1926), Sandford and Arkell (1928), Caton-Thompson and Gardner (1934), Little (1936), Ball (1939), Iskander (1943), Fox (1952), Ibrahim (1951), Shukri and Azer (1952), Shata, Knetsch et al. (1962), Said (1962;1990), Tamer (1968), Shamah (1981), Abdel Kireem (1971), Khalifa (1981), Rifai (1986), Swedan (1986), Bown and Kraus (1988), Youssef, *et al.* (2006) Wanas (2008), Abdel-Fattah, *et al.* (2010), Kusky, *et al.* (2011), Abu El Ghar, (2012) and others.

Figure (2): Geological map of the investigated area after Wanas (2008).

The Middle-Upper Eocene and Oligocene rocks form the main bulk of sediments in the El-Fayoum area. Pliocene and Quaternary sediments are also presented.

The alluvial sediments of the Nile basin were deposited directly over the Plio-Pleistocene sediments. These alluvial sediments that composed of variable sizes sands and gravels are intercalated with silt and clay contents (Tamer, 1968). The Lacustrine deposits of Pleistocene are composed of claystone, gypsum, and calcareous materials intercalated with ferruginous sandy silt. In El-Fayoum depression, Quaternary sediments are directly overlying the limestone deposits of Eocene age.

Based on the previous stratigraphic studies, a brief description of the stratigraphic sequence exposed in El-Fayoum can be summarised in the following:

2.2.1. Holocene deposits:

Holocene deposits are represented by Aeolian sands sheets which cover large domains of the El-Fayoum depression, especially around Qarun Lake and El-Rayan Lakes. In the southwestern part, there are several linear dunes with an NW-SE trend.

2.2.2. Pleistocene deposits:

A. Qena Formation:

Said (1962) termed the Qena Formation for a Quaternary sand sequence cropping out at Qena, with a thickness of 20 m. Its sediments composed of alternating of cross-bedded occasionally consolidated coarse-grained sand and thin beds of gravels. In El-Fayoum area, the Qena Formation that developed in the southwestern part of the area is formed of massive to cross bedded fluvial sands, interbedded with loose sand dune.

B. Gypsum deposits:

The gypsum crusts are recorded only capping the Middle Eocene carbonate rocks that are interbedded with thick gypsiferous shale beds in the north central part of Egypt. Gypsum deposits are recorded in the vicinity of El-Fayoum cultivated lands, extending mainly along its eastern and western boundaries. Generally, they are found in a sheet-like layer, unconformable overlying older rocks of Eocene Ravine beds

(Gehannam Formation) that consist of gypsiferous shale, marl, limestone and sandstone (Strougo and Haggag, 1984). According to Said (1981), the gypseous soil is Early Late Pleistocene age which indicates deposition at an interval of aridity. In some places, these gypsum deposits are covered with a thin layer of flint mixed with sand. This type of sediment is probably lacustrine, i.e. deposited in a shallow body of water isolated from the main sea and completely evaporated. This suggests a playa lake. Three horizons of gypcrete have been identified from bottom to top: (1) massive mottled gypcrete, (2) massive indurated gypcrete, and (3) massive powdery gypcrete (Aref, 2003).

C. Diatomites:

Diatomitic clay is found as isolated patches of low elevation ranging between 36 and 23 m below sea level. Their thickness ranging from 0.6 to 5.4 m. Diatomites is recorded north and southwest of El-Fayoum Province. In the north, they are found north and northeast of Birket Qarun. Two types of Diatomites may be distinguished: a light-colored sandy type and a dark colored clayey type. When both types are found together, the former is the dominant one and always found in the upper part of the succession.

D. Gisir El-Hadid terraces:

The Gisir El-Hadid terraces are made of pebbles and gravels of flint, sandstone and limestone rock fragments, together with some mollusk shell fragments derived from the nearby Eocene sediments. They constitute a narrow strip bounding the western fringe of El-El-Fayoum depression west of the Khata Village.

2.2.3. Pliocene deposits:

The Pliocene sediments of the Nile valley consist of a lower marine sequence of Early Pliocene age and an upper fluvial sequence of Late Pliocene age (Said, 1990). Kusky, *et al.* (2011) termed Kom El-Shelul Formation for Pliocene deposits in Gabal Naalun area. The Kom El-Shelul Formation consists of about a 30 m thick marine section of sandstones and coquinal limestone. This marine succession is followed by a 10 m bed of nonfossiliferous yellow and brownish sandstone with flint pebbles. This bed is probably of fluvial origin and belongs to a Late Pliocene river

system of deposition, which followed the Early Pliocene marine ingressions (Hamblin, 1987).

2.2.4. Miocene deposits:

Miocene deposits in El-Fayoum are represented by the Khashab Formation. It is composed of different colored sand, easily solidifies and shows cross-layering of sand and pebbles with fragments of silicified wood at the top of the Wedan El Faras basalt. The maximum thickness of the formation is 14.8 m at the Khashab Wedan El Faras hill (Swedan, 1986). The best natural outcrops of the Khashab formation are the basalt layers where north, northwest and west of the Wedan El Faras hill (Bown and Kraus, 1988).

2.2.5. Oligocene:

A- Basalt:

The first description of Egyptian Tertiary basalts was in the El-Fayoum depression by Beadnell (1905). These basalt sheets and flows are exposed at Wedan El-Faras and Gabal Qatrani. Basalt flows unconformably overlie the Qatrani Formation. They are extruded during three stages of magmatism in large scale, probably related to the opening of the Red Sea (Meneisy, 1990). El-Sheshtawi (1979) distinguished three successive sheets in the Qatrani basalt after radiometric dating.

B- Qatrani Formation:

In the El-Fayoum depression, Oligocene deposits are described as varicolored sandstones with clay interbeds overlying the fossiliferous beds of the Qasr El-Sagha Formation and underlying the El-Fayoum basalt with a maximum thickness of 340 m (Said, 1990). It is a continental formation deposited by meandering streams and local channel environments to other and transitional types of channels, to floodplain deposits (Gingerich, 1992). It can be divided into an upper sequence composed of sandstones and variegated mudstone, a layer of intermediate guide chalky sandstone coarse to medium-grained, and finally, a sequence dominated by lower friable sandstone coarse gravel almost. There are frequent levels of paleosols and fossil plants and vertebrates (Bown and Kraus, 1988). The sedimentological analysis suggests a local source for these sediments. In the southwestern part of the El-Fayoum area, the Qatrani Formation thins out where it is only 50 m thick, consisting of grayish white to

yellowish brown sandstone, cross-bedded in parts, with quartz pebbles and thin clay interbeds.

2.2.6. Upper Eocene deposits:

The Upper Eocene rocks in the study area represented by two stratigraphic rock units, Birket Qarun and Qasr El Sagha formations that can be described from top to bottom in the following:

A- Qasr El-Sagha Formation:

Qasr El-Sagha series term was used to describe beds full of *Carolia* for about 200 m of crossed bedded sand, sandy mud, limestone and carbonaceous shale that makes up the lower of the escarpments bounding the north margin of El-Fayoum Depression (Beadnell, 1905). It conformably overlies the Birket Qarun Formation and underlies Qatrani Formation of Oligocene Period. The term of Beadnell "series" replaced with "formation" by Simons (1968). Qasr El Sagha Formation composed of sandy and chalky mudstone, sandstone stratified cross-beds carbonaceous shale, with a total thickness of approximately 200 m (Youssef, *et al.* 2006). It characterized by an abundance of plants and animal's fossils, including vertebrates, both terrestrial and marine. The sequence can be divided into different members, corresponding to the alternation of the lagoon facies, with proportions filler terrigenous variables, and deltaic facies, with channel deposits or front. Bowen and Vondra (1974); Abdel-Fattah, et al. (2010) were classified Qasr El Sagha Formation into two subtypes. The temple subtype comprises the lowermost part of the 123 m thick Qasr El-Sagha Formation that shows thinning in the thickness from west to east and It consists mainly of repeated cycles; each cycle is composed of gypsiferous sandy claystone and sandstone at the base and highly fossiliferous sandy limestone (sandy molluscan packstone or sandy dolostone) at the top of each cycle. Bown and Kraus (1988) referred the upper 77m of Qasr El-Sagha Formation for the first time to the Dir Abu Lifa Member and the type section of the Dir Abu Lifa Member is between Dir Abu Lifa and Garet el Esh. This subtype shows eight main units from top to bottom as in the following:

1 - Upper cross- stratified sandstone,

- 2 - Limestone that were deposited behind a bar,
- 3 - Lower cross- stratified sandstone,
- 4 - gypsum-based, gold-colored sandstone sequence,
- 5 - Green sandstone sequence,
- 6 - Sandstone and gypsum sequence,
- 7 - Greenish to golden- colored clayey sandstone sequence,
- 8 - Mighty cross- stratified sandstone sequence.

B- Birket Qarun Formation:

Rocks belonging to this formation were first depicted by Beadnell (1905) as the *Operculina- Nummulites* beds to describe 50m thick, composed of sandstone and shale with few bands of limestone. This formation appears to be the equivalent of the *Operculina* beds (quarried limestone) of the Mokattam Formation (Said, 1990). This series are well exposed in the desert separating El-Fayoum depression from the Nile Valley; on the southwest and east sides of the former; along the northern boundary of the cultivation and Birket Qarun; and westward in the cliffs beyond the outlying hills of the Qaret Gehannam. The maximum measured thickness is 80 m at Um Regle northwest Birket Qarun. It is mainly made up of sandstones calcareous, yellow, medium, fine and a fine cross-bedding with gypsum veins, frequently bioturbated (Abdel-Fattah, *et al.* 2010). The central part contains dark grey shale layer of variable thickness while the top part is characterized by presence of large concretions embedded in coarse cross-bedded sandstone.

2.2.6. Middle Eocene deposits:

Abdel-Fattah, et al. (2010) classified the Middle Eocene deposits into two rock units; Gehannam (Ravine) and Wadi Rayan formations while Iskander (1943) classified the Middle Eocene of El-Fayoum depression into six rock units. These are Samalut, El- Muweilih, Midawara, Sath El Hadid, El Gharaq and Gehannam (Ravine) Formations.

1. Ravine or Gehannam Formation:

Beadnell (1905) used the term “Ravine beds” in describing El Naalun and El Lahun sections for a unit consisting of nummulitic limestone at the top and fossiliferous marl in the base. Further north and westward, the formation includes bioturbated sandy marl and clay interbeds, where it is often referred to as 'Gehannam' (Said, 1962). The depositional environment is mainly shallow waters of an open bay (Gingerich, 1992). It is made up of dark grey, calcareous mudstones, with gypsum veinlets intercalated with greyish white argillaceous limestone and calcareous sandstone with highly bioturbated (Abdel-Fattah, *et al.* 2010). The Gehannam Formation reaches its maximum thickness at Qaret Gehannam section (40 m thick). It conformably overlies the Gharaq Formation and unconformably underlies the Birket Qarun Formation. According to Strougo and Haggag (1984), Abdallah, *et al.* (2002) and Helal (2002) the age of this formation is Late Middle Eocene (Bartonian).

2. El Gharaq Formation:

El Gharaq Formation is the thickest formation of the Wadi El-Rayan Series reaching 124 m at El Bireig in the SE of Wadi El Rayan (Beadnell, 1905; Iskander, 1943). This formation conformably overlies the Sath El Hadid Formation and unconformably underlies the Gehannam Formation. El Gharaq Formation is made of a white limestone packed with large nummulites at the base, and nummulitic marly limestone and siltstone with glauconite, and marly sandstone at the top. It is capped by the Schizaster libycus Sandstone. According to Abdallah, *et al.* (2002) El Gharaq Formation belongs to Late Lutetian.

3. Sath EL Hadid Formation:

It is composed of a reef limestone bank with different sizes of *Nummulites*. Its thickness of about 28 meter decreases in the northeast direction (Abu El Ghar, 2012). Sath El Hadid Formation covers most of the isolated flat hills in Wadi El-Rayan area. Iskander (1943) dated this Formation to Late Lutetian.

4. Midawara Formation:

Midawara Formation composed of limestone intercalated with claystone (Iskander, 1943). It is formed at Gabel Munqar El-Rayan at middle Lutetian time and occurs as mesas in the Wadi El-Rayan area. Midawara Formation formed from brown shale, sandy shale, sandy limestone, and glauconitic sand (Zalmout, 2008). It changed to more calcareous facies; this formation conformably overlies the Muweilih Formation and conformably underlies Sath El Hadid Formation.

.5. Muweilih Formation:

Iskander (1943) mentioned that there is physical uniformity in the transition of between Muweilih and Midawara formations. Muweilih Formation is formed at Gabel Munqar El-Rayan at Early Lutetian age and consists of nummulitic, shaley, sandy, hard limestone and marl (Abu El-Ghar, 1991). The base of the Muweilih Formation is conformably Samalut Formation while the upper contact lie conformable with the overlying Midawara Formation (Abdallah, *et al.* 2002).

6. Samalut Formation:

Samalut Formation is the oldest rock unit that recorded in the extreme southern part of the study area. This formation is unconformable with the overlying El Muweilih Formation. This is clear at the entrance of Wadi El Muweilih from the Nile Valley. It is recognized by the presence of iron concretions and gypsum nodules while the lower contact unexposed. It can be recognized at 10 km south the study area by the occurrence of the concretions between the snow white limestone of the uppermost Minia Formation and nummulitic limestone of the Samalut Formation. It is composed of greyish white and yellow nummulites limestone. Abdallah, *et al.* (2002) dated Samalut Formation as Middle Eocene age (Early Lutetian), according to its faunal content.

2.3. Structural Setting:

As mentioned in the previous work of Said (1962), Tamer (1968), Swedan (1986); Kusky, *et al.* (2011), El-Fayoum district bounded on all sides by faults and folds as shown in Figure (3).

Figure (3): Structural map of El-Fayoum depression after Massoud *et al.* (2009)

These faults play an important role in the occurrence and flow of groundwater aquifers. The most common structural elements in the study area can be summarized in the following:

1. Unconformity:

In the study area, a major unconformity is observed, especially in the east at El-Nazla, Shaqluf, east of Sela, Gabal El-Naalun, and Gabal El-Lahun where the post-Eocene deposits are unconformable with the Eocene sediments.

2. Faults:

Blanckenhorn (1901) stated that El-Fayoum depression is a closed triangular basin bounded by faults on all sides. This opinion is thought to be baseless, since

observed faults are not parallel to the edges of the depression but considerably slant to the basin, and oriented mainly NW-SE and E-W trends (Kusky, *et al.* 2011). In the following a detailed discussion of the major fault trends will be made:

a- NW-SE Trend (Clysmic Trend):

This fault trend dissects the Eocene rocks at the east of Mishigiga area. Its down-throw at the east, displacing the basement complex by 1000 feet. Another one affected the area west of Mishigiga, which dipping toward the west (Bayoumi and El Gamili, 1970). To the north of Birket Qarun, especially at Qasr El-Sagha Temple, Garet El-Gindi, and Gabal Qatrani, the Upper Eocene rocks are also affected by an NW-SE fault.

b- E-W Trend (Tethyan Trend):

A set of E-W striking faults has been observed in the north and east of El-Fayoum area, especially at Gabal Qatrani and the Nile- Fayoum divide. El-Shazly (1966) suggested that this fault is dated as Late Pliocene age being relevant to the development of the Mediterranean. E-W strike-slip faults cut the Qatrani basalt with a displacement of about 2 km. E-W faults affect the Pliocene and the Quaternary deposits of the Nile- Fayoum divides especially at Shaqluf, Demu, Gerza areas, dipping northward except in Demu area it dips southward (Kusky, *et al.* 2011).

c- NE-SW Trend (Aqaba Trend):

This trend is considered as the western fault of the Nile graben. It is largely represented in the north and west of Birket Qarun and north of Gabal Qatrani. The influence of these faults is limited to their immediate neighborhood.

3. Folds:

Swedan (1986) mentioned that Middle Eocene deposits affected by folds in the western and south-western portion of the study area. Some of the Upper Eocene sandstones affected by an NW-SE fault which passes into a fold before dying out.

Chapter Three

Hydrogeology

The irrigation and agricultural system in the Fayoum district depend mainly on River Nile water. El-Fayoum city, the Capital of the governorate, is a water distribution center for El-Fayoum (domestic demands) and a network of canals and small pumping stations deliver water to the agricultural regions. The water-bearing formation has a widely geographical distribution in the study area and differs greatly in their extension, potentialities and source of recharge. The description of hydrogeological condition of El-Fayoum depression will be discussed with respect to the following items:

3.1. Climatic Elements:

The study area is a part of Upper Egypt which lies within the arid belt of North Africa. The climate of the study area is hot and dry in summer, being mild with rare rainfalls in winter. The climatic element represents one of the main parameter which affects the hydrogeological evaluation of the groundwater resources in the study area. The climatic variables include the data of an average of the minimum and maximum air temperature, relative humidity, evaporation, and rainfall. These data were obtained from the stations located at and around El-Fayoum city (Egyptian Meteorological Authority, 2010).

3.1.1. Air temperature:

The air temperature plays an important role on the evaporation and evapotranspiration rate in the area. From the recorded temperature values, it was noted that the temperature ranges from 35.1 °C to 46.7 °C in summer months and from 18°C to 21.5°C during winter months. The calculated mean monthly value is 22°C.

3.1.2. Relative Humidity (RH %):

The relative humidity is a measure of the amount of water vapor in the air (at a specific temperature) compared to the maximum amount of water vapor air could hold

at that temperature, and is given as a percentage value. Relative humidity depends on the temperature of the air; as warm air can hold more moisture than the cold air. It plays the main role in determining the amount of evaporation, evapotranspiration and dew condensation. From the collected data, the maximum monthly mean value of relative humidity is 64.5% during January, while the minimum monthly mean is 44% during May. The total monthly mean value of the relative humidity at El-Fayoum district is 53.7%.

3.1.3. Evaporation and Evapotranspiration:

Evaporation is the change of a liquid into a vapor at a temperature below the boiling point. It takes place at the surface of a liquid, where molecules with the highest kinetic energy are able to escape. When this happens, the average kinetic energy of the liquid is lowered, and its temperature decreases. Evaporation from vegetation is generally given a more specific term evapotranspiration or ET for short. By definition, ET is the loss of water from a vegetated surface through the combined processes of soil evaporation and plant transpiration. The evaporation rate is a function of air temperature, relative air humidity, and wind velocity. It affects both the surface water and groundwater, particularly when the level of the latter one close to the ground surface. Data from the Organization of Meteorology in Egypt refers to the maximum monthly mean value of evaporation and evapotranspiration are 10 mm/day and 7.6 mm/day during July respectively, while the minimum monthly mean are 3.5 mm/day and 3.13 mm/day during January respectively.

3.1.4. Rainfall:

Rain is liquid water in the form of droplets that have condensed from atmospheric water vapor and then precipitated that is, become heavy enough to fall under gravity. It is a major component of the water cycle and also responsible for depositing most of the fresh water on the Earth. It provides suitable conditions for many types of ecosystem, as well as water for hydroelectric power plants and crop irrigation. The climate in the study area is very hot and dry, despite a small average annual rainfall. The mean annual rainfall at all stations in the Study area is very low (13.2 mm at Komoshem, 10.75 mm at Fayoum and 9.2 mm at Shakshok station). The

very low amounts of precipitation falling in the winter half year, with the months December, January, and February, 55% of the rainfall omitted. June, July, August, and September are rainless. In the study area, as in most of the arid region, brief heavy rain with high intensity can be occurred.

3.2. Surface water resources:

El-Fayoum district is connected to River Nile by a canal called Bahr Yousif, which is considered the main source of the surface water in the study area. El-Fayoum depression has a dense net of irrigation canals and drains covering major parts of the depression as shown in Figure (4).

Figure (4): Irrigation and drain canals within El-Fayoum depression

a- The irrigation system:

The amount of irrigation water of El-Fayoum district varies from one year to another with an average 2.17×10^9 m³/year. This amount of water is passing through

Bahr Yousif which enters El-Fayoum depression at Hawaret El-Maktaa with a length 11 km. This canal branches into several small canals (Bahr El-Nazla with a length 12 km and Bahr Wahbi with a length 60 km) which carry the irrigation water to cultivated lands (Shedid, 1994).

b- The drainage system:

The slope of the landscape plays an important role in the drainage system of El-Fayoum depression. The surface of the cultivated land and the surrounding desert in the depression generally slope towards north and west. Lake Qarun and Wadi El-Rayan lakes are used as a general discharge points for agricultural wastewater and sewage waters. The main drains in El-Fayoum depression are:

- El-Bats drain: this drain collects agricultural drainage waters from the eastern and northeastern parts of the Fayoum watershed with a length of 50.8 km and a maximum depth of 25 m, decrease gradually toward Lake Qarun. The total water salinity of it is less than 2 ppm (Shedid, 1994).
- El-Wadi drain: this drain receives drainage water from the middle region of El-Fayoum depression with a length of 48.5 km. The total water salinity of this drain is less than 2.5 ppm (Shedid, 1994).
- Other drains: these drains discharge directly into Lake Qarun such as Said, Abu Turfayia, Khour El-Hitan and Ahariut drains. Their average water salinity is less than 3 ppm (Shedid, 1994).

3.3. Lakes:

Two lakes are found at El-Fayoum depression, lake Qarun, and Wadi el-Rayan. Lake Qarun is a saline remnant of the historical freshwater Lake Moeris with a maximum length of 45 km and a maximum width of 9 km (Ball, 1939). It was connected to River Nile water through the period of its formation at 1980 bc till the Ptolemaic Period (323–246 bc) (El-Shabrawy and Dumont, 2009). The lake exhibits increase in salinity, especially during the twentieth century because the lake is no longer supplied by River Nile water and used as a general receiver for both sewage waters and drainage wastewater that evaporates in its basin. Its total salinity increased

gradually from a brackish to a hypersaline state. In Wadi El-Rayan area, two successive lakes, separated by a waterfall, were created as a receiver for drainage wastewater.

a- Lake Qarun:

Lake Qarun is saline lake occupying the deepest part of El-Fayoum Depression in the western desert of Egypt with an attitude of ≈ 43 m below sea level (Fig.5). It is located between the Longitudes of $30^{\circ} 24'$ & $30^{\circ} 49'$ E and Latitudes of $29^{\circ} 24'$ & $29^{\circ} 33'$ N with an area of 240 km^2 and capacity of $1.19 \times 10^9 \text{ m}^3$. About 67% of the lake has a depth of between 2 and 5 m while 18% of the lake is deeper than 5 m (Baioumy, et al., 2010). The mean depth of Lake Qarun is 5.7 m and the deepest region (≈ 10 m) is located in the middle part of the lake while the shallowest region lies in the eastern portion of the lake (Shedid, 1994). To the north, the lake is completely covered by rock and sand exposures without any marks of vegetation while, in the south and southeast, the area is totally cultivated land that slopes towards the lake which makes it a natural basin for drainage water and wastewater (Aleem, 1958). The annual quantity of drainage water diverted into lake Qarun is $338 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3/\text{year}$ from the El-Bats and El-Wadi drains and about $67.8 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3/\text{year}$ from groundwater, carrying an average of $470 \times 10^6 \text{ kg}$ of salts (Rasmy and Estefan, 1983) while it loses about $415 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3/\text{year}$ by evaporation (Meshal, 1973; Keatings, et al., 2007; Ellah, 2009). Lake Qarun water is currently alkaline, saline and turbid. The water temperature ranges seasonally between about 15 and 33°C (Ball, 1939; El-Sayed and Guindy, 1999). Water level usually rises in spring and drops in late summer and early autumn. The minimum level (-45.1 m) is in September, while the maximum level (-43.4 m) in May. The mean water level of Lake Qarun is about 44 m below sea level (Meshal and Morcos, 1984). During winter, the drainage water inflow to the lake exceeds the water loss by evaporation, possibly elevating the lake water level leading to flooding in these seasons. In fact, the annual water storage of Lake Qarun can vary annually. The rate of evaporation in fresh water is high in Lake Qarun due to the decrease in the saturation vapor pressure over the surface of the highly saline water of the lake.

Figure (5): Digital elevation map showing the land slopes from Lahun to Lake Qarun (Wahed, et al., 2015).

The volume of evaporation is directly proportional to the surface water level and the area of the lake (Shedid, 1994). The agricultural drainage water and sewage water are the main source of inflow to Lake Qarun while the main source of outflow from the lake is the evaporation from the open surface area of the lake. The net water budget in Lake Qarun is negative by about $96 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3 \text{ y}^{-1}$ (El-Shabrawy and Dumont, 2009).

b- Wadi El-Rayan lakes:

Wadi El Rayan depression is an uninhabited depression in Egypt's Western Desert, located southwest of Fayoum Province at 60 m below sea level, and has an estimated area of 703 km². It lies between Latitudes 28° 45' and 29° 20'N and Longitudes 30° 15' and 30° 35'E. Since 1973, two parts has been used as a receiver for agricultural drainage water and sewage water to reduce the water level in Lake Qarun. Two artificial lakes that present in Wadi El Rayan are upper and lower lakes which connected by small canal. The upper lake is surrounded by dense vegetation and covers an area of approximately 53 km² at an elevation of 10 m below sea level with a maximum depth of 25 m (Saleh, 1984). The lower lake receives the excess water of the upper lake via a shallow connecting channel. The lower lake covers an area of

approximately 110 km² at an elevation of 18 m below sea level (Mansour and Sidky, 2003). The recorded maximum water depth in the lower lake is 33 m (Ellah, 2009). The upper lake gains water about $220 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3 \text{ y}^{-1}$ from the El-Wadi Drain, while annual discharge to the lower lake is $127 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3 \text{ y}^{-1}$ (Ellah, 2009). The net water budget for the upper lake used to have a positive value of $13 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3 \text{ y}^{-1}$, for the lower lake $39 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3 \text{ y}^{-1}$. The above mentioned values are recently become negative (El-Shabrawy and Dumont, 2009). The area and volume of Wadi El Rayan lakes vary with the fluctuation in its surface water level, where they increase with time due to the continuous filling of the depression with drainage water. The surface water level of the upper and the lower lake is 10 m and 20 m below sea level respectively. The lakes vary in physical and chemical characters; these features will be considered in detail later on. Wadi El Rayan depression is situated in the arid region. Its climate is hot and dry with scanty winter rain and abundant sunshine throughout the year (Smith, 1983). The air temperature varies from 48.5°C in June to 1.2°C in January. The minimum and maximum evaporation rate, 3.18 cm month⁻¹ and 25.67 cm month⁻¹, were recorded in autumn and summer, respectively. Relative humidity varies from 37% and 58% in June and November (El-Shabrawy and Dumont, 2009)

3.4. Groundwater aquifers:

The detailed geological and geophysical studies revealed presence of three aquifers units in the study area. Brief description of these aquifers is given in the following:

3.4.1. The Quaternary aquifer:

The Quaternary aquifer represents the main water bearing formation in the study area. It occupies the main portion of Fayoum Depression. This aquifer has a widely distribution in Nile Valley and its vicinities. It was not record in Wadi El Rayan depression. The Quaternary aquifer is composed mainly of a successive layer of sands and gravels. These sediments are intercalated with clay and silt. The thickness of this aquifer is differing from one location to another, and generally is thinning towards Wadi El Rayan depression. The sediments of this aquifer are mostly underlain by Pliocene Clay and Eocene Limestone which forms the base of

Quaternary aquifer. The groundwater of Quaternary aquifer occurs under free conditions in two essential forms (free surface water table and springs) in major parts of the study area. El-Fayoum depression is considered as one of the most important regions in Egypt having a large number of natural springs.

Based on the data obtained from the drilled wells in the study area as shown in Figure (6), the following hydrogeological conditions can be recognized:

Figure (6): Location of the collected water samples

- The depth to the groundwater surface and its flow direction mainly depends on the topography of the study area.
- The depth of water in the Quaternary aquifer decreases toward the north (Lake Qarun) and in the area near the main canals and drains due to the downward seepage of surface water from them to the aquifer as shown in Figure (7).
- Based on the previous work, there is no great change in depth of water from the Quaternary aquifer with the time.
- The water level of the Quaternary aquifer decreases from the south and southeastern portions of the depression (21 m) toward Lake Qarun north the depression (-42 m).
- The direction of groundwater flow is mainly towards the topographically low areas i.e. towards Lake Qarun (north direction).
- In the study area, the Quaternary aquifer is mainly recharged by the percolation of applied irrigation water, leakage of groundwater from the underlying Eocene fractured limestone aquifer and seepage of soil water from the nearby cultivated lands.
- The discharge from the aquifer is occurred by pumping wells which used for irrigation purposes and the seepage toward Lake Qarun and lowland areas in the depression. The possible evaporation from the groundwater surface of this aquifer is tack place in some localities.
- The transmissivity of this aquifer ranging between 8.3×10^{-4} and 1.7×10^{-2} m²/ min (Desert Reserch Institute, 1986).
- Most of El-Fayoum springs are the perennial type and their origin coming from infiltration from irrigated lands because of the water level in springs are higher than the corresponding groundwater level.

Figure (7): Depth to water contour map 2016 (groundwater samples)

3.4.2. Eocene aquifer:

Based on the geological studies the Eocene rocks have wide distribution in the study area either on surface or in the subsurface. Samalute Formation represents Eocene aquifer unit in the study area and made up of snow white, hard, highly fossiliferous limestone with marl and shale intercalations. Eocene Limestone is fractured and is probably affected by a network of faulting system (Said, 1981). These faults are acting as hydraulic boundaries between Eocene Limestone and younger water-bearing rocks. Eocene sediments are considered as a water bearing formation of poor quality and limited quantity in the study area. (Tamer, *et al.* 1975) detected the limestone and marl series in the subsurface and has amount thickness of about 300 m between Beni-Suef and Fayoum.

The groundwater of the Eocene aquifer occurs under confined conditions where it is overlain by the impermeable clay sediments. Two wells which tapped the Eocene aquifer were recorded during this study, that wells are No.10 at Wadi El Rayan depression and No.11 at the northern part of the study area. The total depth of these

wells is 50, 100 m respectively. The water levels of the Eocene aquifer in these wells are -25, -34 m. The possible recharge of the Eocene Limestone aquifer in the study area may occur through upward leakage from the underlying Cretaceous aquifer. The discharge of this aquifer is mainly occurred through vertical leakage to the overlying Quaternary aquifer, evaporation Wadi El Rayan depression, and seepage toward Lake Qarun.

3.4.3. Cretaceous aquifer:

The Cretaceous aquifer has a wide distribution in the subsurface of the Western Desert. The sediments of these aquifers are not recorded up till now in the subsurface of El-Fayoum depression but it has a wide geographic distribution in the subsurface at Wadi El Rayan depression at a depth of about 700 m with total thickness 450 m. It is composed mainly of sandstone and limestone with shale intercalation. This aquifer recharges the Eocene aquifer through upward leakage (Abdel-Baki, 1972).

3.5. The Hydrological relation between El-Fayoum lakes and the surrounding aquifers:

According to the previous studies, the source of groundwater under El-Fayoum depression coming from infiltration from soil water and surface water as well as the leakage from the underlying Eocene and Cretaceous aquifers. In the following a detailed discussion of hydrological and hydrogeological relationships of El-Fayoum lakes with surrounding aquifer:

- The Quaternary aquifer acts as a discharge area for the Eocene aquifer where the groundwater level of Quaternary aquifer is lower than that of the Eocene aquifer and recharge area for Qarun Lake as the water level of the aquifer is higher than that of Qarun Lake.
- Wadi El Rayan depression acts as a recharge area for the Quaternary aquifer. Therefore, it acting as indirect recharging source for Qarun Lake.
- The Eocene aquifer discharges into Qarun Lake all over El-Fayoum depression.

Conclusion

The study area is considered as one of the most land reclamation projects in the Western Desert of Egypt. It is bounded by latitudes 29°00', 29°45'N and longitudes 30°15', 31°15'E. The exploited amounts of groundwater are actually very limited in this area. In the study area, a relatively thick sedimentary section occurs. This section is ranging in age from Eocene to Recent age. Two aquifers were detected in the study area represented by Quaternary and Eocene limestone aquifers. The main aim of the thesis is investigating the groundwater conditions of the available aquifers in the reclaimed lands around El-Fayoum depression based on geological, and geophysical, hydrogeological and hydrogeochemical studies.

Geomorphology:

The study area has two main morphotectonic depressions are El-Fayoum and Wadi El-Rayan depressions. The first is a circular depression which covers an area about 1700 km². It is closed with an altitude ranging from +24 m above sea level at Lahun area to -45 m below sea level at Qarun lake. The eastern and northern portion of the depression covered by sediments of Eocene and Oligocene time that are characterized by the absence of any drainage lines and agricultural activity. Wadi El-Rayan depression is isolated and uninhabited depression situated southwest of El-Fayoum, at -60 m below sea level (b.s.l). The depression is separated from El-Fayoum by limestone ridge (Gisr El-Hadid plateau) and is bounded on all sides by highlands e.g., Gabal El-Mishigiega (+96 m b.s.l). The ground surface of Wadi El-Rayan depression is covered by sabkha, sand dunes, and sand plains. El-Fayoum depression contains natural and artificial lakes. The Wadi El-Rayan lakes represented the artificial lakes. The natural lakes are represented by Qarun Lake. The Aeolian landforms in the study area are represented mainly by sand dunes spread in the study area especially in Wadi El-Rayan depression and north of Lake Qarun, Desert pavement is well developed along the eastern flat side and Yardangs Mushroom rocks and ventifacts occur on the western side of El-Fayoum depression especially in Wadi El-Hitan area. The land features in the study area are mainly of sedimentary origin and

represent by the young and old alluvial plains. El-Fayoum depression is surrounded by scarps and structural calcareous plateaux in most parts, like Gabal El-Naalun in the east, Gabal El-lahun in the south, Gabal Qatrani and sandstone of Oligocene time in the north, Gizr El-Hadid plateau in the southwest and Garet Gehannam plateau in the west of the Fayoum depression.

Geology:

The rock units in El-Fayoum depression and its vicinities are of sedimentary origin, ranging in age from Tertiary to Quaternary. The only igneous rocks in the area are represented by basalt sheets in the north of Gabal Qatrani. The alluvial sediments of the Nile basin were deposited directly over the Plio-Pleistocene sediments. Pleistocene lacustrine clastic sediments occur within El Fayoum depression floor. The Pliocene deposits are mostly fluvial sandstones and restrict to Nile-Fayoum divide. There is a series of Lower Miocene red sands and gravels containing silicified tree trunks. These Miocene deposits are well developed at Gabal Khashab (north of Fayoum depression). Underlying the Miocene deposits, there are basalt sheets and Qatrani Formation of Oligocene Age. Qatrani Formation is made up of a series of variegated sands and sandstones, with alternating beds of shale. It is underlain by the Qasr El-Sagha Formation which consists of sandy and chalky mudstone, sandstone stratified cross-beds carbonaceous shale. Underlying the Qasr El-Sagha Formation, there is The Birket Qarun Formation that composed mainly of calcareous sandstones and sandy limestone. It is underlain by the Middle Eocene rocks which are represented by Ravine Formation and Wadi Rayan Formation. The Ravine Formation consists of gypsiferous shale, marls and limestone rich in Operculinae sp. The Wadi Rayan Formation consists of hard, snow-white limestone that contains numerous *Nummulites gizehensis*.

Hydrogeology:

El-Fayoum district is connected to River Nile by a canal called Bahr Youssef, which is considered the main source of the surface water in the study area. El-Fayoum depression has a dense net of irrigation canals and drains covering major parts of the depression. The amount of irrigation water is passing through Bahr Youssef which

enters El-Fayoum depression at Hawaret El-Maktaa with a length 11 km. The slope of the landscape plays an important role in the drainage system of El-Fayoum depression. Lake Qarun and Wadi El-Rayan lakes are used as a general discharge points for agricultural wastewater and sewage waters. The main drains in El-Fayoum depression are El-Bats drain and El-Wadi drain. Two lakes are found at El-Fayoum depression, lake Qarun, and Wadi El-Rayan. Lake Qarun is a saline lake with a maximum length of 45 km and a maximum width of 9 km. The lake exhibits increase in salinity because the lake is no longer supplied by River Nile water and used as a general receiver for both sewage waters and drainage wastewater that evaporates in its basin. Its total salinity increased gradually from a brackish to a hypersaline state. In Wadi El-Rayan area, two successive lakes, separated by a waterfall, were created as a receiver for drainage wastewater. The upper lake covers an area of approximately 53 km² at an elevation of 10 m below sea level with a maximum depth of 25 m. The lower lake receives the excess water of the upper lake via a shallow connecting channel and covers an area of approximately 110 km² at an elevation of 18 m below sea level. The recorded maximum water depth in the lower lake is 33 m. The two lakes vary in physical and chemical characters.

Based on the stratigraphic successions, geophysical survey and drilled well data of the study area, two main aquifers were detected namely, the Quaternary and Eocene limestone aquifers. The Quaternary aquifer represents the main bearing formation in the study area. It occupies the main portion of Fayoum Depression. This aquifer has a widely distribution in Nile Valley and its vicinities. It was not record in Wadi El Rayan depression. It extends in the subsurface with variable thicknesses depending on the shape of the underlying Eocene limestone with maximum thickness is about 34 m. This shallow aquifer is capped with clay sediments (confining layer) so it is considered as a confined aquifer. The depth of water in the Quaternary aquifer decreases toward the north (Lake Qarun) and in the area near the main canals and drains due to the downward seepage of surface water from them to the aquifer. There is no great change in depth to water from the Quaternary aquifer with the time. The depth of water, as encountered from shallow wells in and around the study area, varies from 1 m to 5 m. At some localities, groundwater from Quaternary water-bearing

zones flows as natural springs, for example, Ain El-Siliyin, Ain El-Shaer, and Ain Fidaymin. El-Fayoum depression is considered as one of the most important regions in Egypt having a large number of natural springs. The direction of groundwater flow is mainly towards the topographically low areas i.e. towards Lake Qarun. In the study area, the Quaternary aquifer is mainly recharged by the percolation of applied irrigation water, leakage of groundwater from the underlying Eocene fractured limestone aquifer and seepage of soil water from the nearby cultivated lands. The discharge from the aquifer is occurred by pumping wells which used for irrigation purposes and the seepage toward Lake Qarun and lowland areas in the depression. The possible evaporation from the groundwater surface of this aquifer is take place in some localities. Eocene water-bearing formation is composed of limestone with marl and extending to a depth of about 600 m. The possible recharge of the Eocene limestone aquifer in the study area may occur almost entirely through upward leakage from the underlying Cretaceous aquifer. The discharge of this aquifer is mainly occurred essentially through vertical leakage to the overlying quaternary aquifer. Also, the aquifer discharges into Lake Qarun.

Hydrogeochemistry:

Sixty water samples from boreholes, dug wells, springs and surface water were collected (Fig.6). For fulfilling the gap since there are scarcity in data, water samples were taken from thirty-two bore holes, two springs and twenty-six surface water samples d in February 2014. Water samples were collected in rinsed plastic bottles for chemical analysis. Measuring temperature, total dissolved solids (TDS), electrical Conductivity (EC) and PH were carried in-situ. The major cations such as Na^+ , K^+ , Ca^{++} , Mg^{++} , major anions such as Cl^- , SO_4^{--} , HCO_3^- and minor anions such as NO_3^- were measured for detecting the water quality in central laboratory of El-Fayoum Drinking Water and Sanitation Company. The results of the chemical analysis showed that:

- The water in the study area has a good quality in terms of PH value for the sampled water points.

- The groundwater samples from Quaternary aquifer have electric conductivity values differ from 612 to 13358 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$. The electric conductivity of Eocene aquifer water samples are ranges from 4699 to 33288 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ in well No.10 and well No.11 respectively.
- The salinity of surface water increase toward Lake Qarun. Increases of evaporation rate and dissolution of evaporites are the main reason for the increase of EC and TDS.
- The groundwater salinity values of Quaternary aquifer fluctuate from fresh to slightly saline water where TDS ranges from 410 ppm to 8125 ppm and that of Eocene aquifer varies from moderately saline water to very saline water, since TDS range from 3327 ppm to 22303 ppm.
- There is an increase in the major ion constituents toward the lakes and northward, which is due to the leaching and dissolution processes and the effect of over pumping rates.
- The total hardness of the groundwater in the investigated area is referring to hard - very hard water.
- 61.5% of surface water samples and 61.75 % of groundwater samples have $r_{\text{Na}/r_{\text{Cl}}}$ higher than 1.2, that reflecting Na replaces Ca and Mg in their carbonates. 34.6% of surface water samples and 17.65 % of groundwater samples exhibit values ranging from 1 to 1.2 which indicate alkaline replaces of Ca and Mg in their sulfate and a small part of their carbonates. 3.84% of surface water samples and 17.64 % of groundwater samples has ratio less than unity which indicate that Na replace Ca and Mg in their halogens.
- Surface water samples reflecting that the sulfate is more than chloride except in the Qarun lake and Wadi El-Rayan lakes samples. This can be attributed to the presence of gypsum near irrigation water and abundance of chloride salts in Lake Qarun and Wadi El-Rayan lakes deposits. 34.37% samples of the Quaternary aquifer has an excess of sulfate over chloride due to the presence of gypsum near these wells and 65.63% groundwater sample has an excess of chloride over sulfate which reflecting abundance of chloride salts in the aquifer deposits. In the area study area, Eocene water samples reflect that the

chloride is more than sulfate. This is attributed to the presence of marine deposits in the study area. This refers ability of water in precipitating sulfate salts before chloride salts.

- In the surface water samples, Ca ion excess than Mg, one except in Qarun lake and Wadi El-Rayan lakes samples. 59.37% samples of the Quaternary aquifer have an excess of Ca over Mg, reflecting that the irrigation water recharges the Quaternary aquifer. 40.63% of the Quaternary samples and 50% of the Eocene water samples has an excess of Mg than Ca which attributed to the abundance of clay that acts as ion selectors in the exchanging process. Eocene water samples have Ca content more than Mg as a result of the dissolution of limestone.
- Two main sequences of combination between cations and anions have been deduced in the surface water as follows:

Assemblage I; $\text{Ca}(\text{HCO}_3)_2$, $\text{Mg}(\text{HCO}_3)_2$, MgSO_4 , Na_2SO_4 , and NaCl

Assemblage II; $\text{Ca}(\text{HCO}_3)_2$, CaSO_4 , MgSO_4 , Na_2SO_4 , and NaCl

- For the groundwater samples, three main sequences are recognized as follows:

Assemblage I; $\text{Ca}(\text{HCO}_3)_2$, $\text{Mg}(\text{HCO}_3)_2$, MgSO_4 , Na_2SO_4 , and NaCl

Assemblage II; $\text{Ca}(\text{HCO}_3)_2$, CaSO_4 , MgSO_4 , Na_2SO_4 , and NaCl

Assemblage III; $\text{Ca}(\text{HCO}_3)_2$, CaSO_4 , MgSO_4 , MgCl_2 , and NaCl

Salt assemblages No.I and II revealing that groundwater are directly connected with the surface water.

- Surface water has ion dominance in the head of irrigation system $\text{Ca} > \text{Na} > \text{Mg}$ among cations and $\text{HCO}_3 > \text{SO}_4 > \text{Cl}$ among anions. It became $\text{Na} > \text{Ca} > \text{Mg}$ among cations and $\text{HCO}_3 > \text{SO}_4 > \text{Cl}$ among anions as water flow toward lakes. Qarun lake and upper lake of Wadi El-Rayan has ion dominance $\text{Na} > \text{Mg} > \text{Ca}$ as the dominated cations and $\text{Cl} > \text{SO}_4 > \text{HCO}_3$ as the dominated anions. The dominant chemical water types of the surface water are Ca-HCO_3 , Na-HCO_3 and Na-Cl .
- Groundwater has Na as the dominant cation, while the dominant anion is greatly variable. The chemical dominant water type of groundwater samples

are Na_2SO_4 , NaCl and NaHCO_3 . The sodium bicarbonate water type reflects the recharge of Quaternary aquifer is from surface water. The presence of NaCl water type can be attributed to mixing of Quaternary water with the underlying Eocene one along some fault plains, the dissolution of halite and the extensive use of fertilizers. In the groundwater of the Eocene aquifer, the chemical water type is sodium – chloride. This chemical water type of the Eocene aquifer reflects the impact of the marine fades and leaching dissolution processes.

- The water samples were plotted on Piper’s diagram (Piper, 1944). As shown in Fig.5, 73% of Surface water and 55.88 % of groundwater lies in sector (1) which, indicating primary alkalinity characteristics (primary salinity). Mixed water type represents 41.17% of groundwater samples and 7.69% Surface water samples. The rest of groundwater samples and surface water samples are lies in sector (4), which reflect secondary salinity properties.
- According to the U.S. salinity lab classification and Wilcox diagram, irrigation water samples located in (C2-S1, C3-S1) class, reflecting a good quality and high suitability for irrigation purposes while 28.13 % samples of Quaternary aquifer are occupies the classes (C2-S1, C3-S1). It is noticed from these classes that, the groundwater of Quaternary aquifer may be considered suitable for irrigation use, 62.5 % samples of Quaternary aquifer and 50% of Eocene water samples fall in (C4-S2 and C4-S3) classes and the rest outside the diagram. It is clear from these classes that, the groundwater of these samples is not suitable for irrigation under ordinary condition due to its high salinity, but special management for salinity control may be required and salt tolerant plants should be selected.

Geophysical studies:

The combination of interpreted electrical resistivity and borehole data has successfully established the nature and configuration of Quaternary and Eocene aquifers within the study area. The geoelectrical sounding results allow a distinction to be made between the groundwater saturated zone and the high-resistivity partially saturated massive limestone zone at the southern and western part of the area, as well

as the low-resistivity brackish water saturated zone in the northern part. Moreover, the low quality groundwater zone in the area was delineated accurately. Although, in most of the area, the water is normally brackish, with TDS ranging between 410 and 8950 ppm, it may serve acute water needs especially for agricultural and industrial purposes. From the interpreted electrical data the Quaternary aquifer is composed of sand to sandy clay deposits and exhibit low thickness and resistivity ranges. The uppermost part of the Eocene aquifer was detected and consists of fractured limestone and marly limestone with high resistivity values and low groundwater potentiality. Geoelectrical depth soundings, when used in conjunction with borehole data, may reduce costs substantially by reducing the number of failed drill holes. In turn, future well locations can be placed with more confidence than before and will subsequently lead to a better understanding of groundwater movement and quality in the context of a feasibility study. Characterizing the hydrogeology of this type of aquifer requires accurate information regarding its geometry; parameters such as porosity, permeability, water salinity, and water recharge are also important for evaluating potential sources of potable groundwater.

Recommendations

Based on the results of this study, it is recommend that:

- Change the irrigation system from flood to drip and sprinkler irrigation in the areas surfing from water logging.
- Establish an effective system for the agriculture drainage over all the study area.
- Select the proper crops on basis of groundwater quality in the area in order to minimize the yield reduction.
- Detailed plan of hydrogeological and reliable groundwater management studies is recommended for controlling the groundwater conditions in the study area.
- Land reclamation projects are not recommended as low quality and potentiality of groundwater in the study area.